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Development of large lab-scale fire dynamics experiments relevant for Scandinavian wildfire behaviour

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Abstract. The Scandinavian countries have in later years seen several severe wildfires and is expected to exhibit more severe fire danger. While direct flame spread has been an important topic in wildfire research, there is a need for development and to ensure that experimental methods are relevant for Scandinavian wildfire characteristics. To ensure relevant lab conditions for fire-resilient material development work, large lab-scale (2×4 meters) experiments were conducted on various fuels. Its fire behaviour (such as rate of spread, fireline intensity and flame length) was compared with ongoing wildfire field studies from ongoing field studies in boreal and hemiboreal Sweden. The lab fire experiments show good potential to mimic relevant natural wildfire conditions in the laboratory once a standard design fire exposure for fire resilient materials is developed.

1. Introduction

Worldwide, wildfires cost 310 lives in 2023 alone [1] and 50 billion dollars in materials yearly [2], and the loss of buildings during wildfires is an increasing challenge [3]. The 2023 Maui wildfire, claiming 97 lives [4], and the 2018 Mati Greece wildfire, claiming 99 lives, are examples of severe wildfires [5]. The severe Scandinavian wildfire season of 2018 [6,7] and the winter wildfires of 2014 [8] are examples of recent north European fires scorching vast areas and with high consequences for the built environment. The threat to buildings put the wildland-urban interface areas (WUIs) at highest preventative priority when implementing measures to reduce the consequences of wildfires.

The Scandinavian countries have in later years seen an increase in wildfire severity and frequency and is expected to experience more severe future fire danger [9,10]. Several fires have started in abandoned heathlands with old heather and presence of juniper, pine and spruce [11]. Norway, with a long coastline and stretched-out landmass, and Sweden, with large boreal forest areas, have many rural areas with buildings and infrastructure close to coniferous fuels or unmanaged cultural landscapes. A common building ignition mechanism in this area is direct flame contact and is therefore considered the main avenue in which to mitigate damages [12–14]. Many fire-resilient materials and products used for protecting buildings and infrastructure exist on the market but without suitable experiments it is difficult to assess their adequacy or cost-effectiveness. Several such methods have been proposed [15–17], and in this study, we explore how to best mimick Scandinavian wildfires on heathlands and boreal forests in laboratory conditions, considering heathland and boreal forest floor fire

characteristics. The aim is a large lab-scale (2-4 meters) experimental method for relevant and repeatable laboratory documentation of reaction to fire properties of WUI area materials and products.

2. Experimental setup

The experimental setup consisted of non-combustible 0.6 cm thick (“Steni Masterboard”) plates (set-up size $Y=250\text{ cm} \times X=402\text{ cm}$) connected to a steel frame placed on four individual load cells (maximum load capacity 800 kg, with 0.1 kg uncertainty). The fuel bed size was $235\text{ cm} \times 394.5\text{ cm}$, fuel height 5 cm for wood chips and 8-10 cm for wood fibre. The bed height was $5 \pm 1\text{ cm}$ for wood chips and 5-10 cm for wood fibre. A fibre board ($235\text{ cm} \times 5\text{ cm} \times 1.2\text{ cm}$) soaked with 2.3 dL isopropanol was used as wick for ignition. Experiments with tilt were inclined by 20° (Figure 4).

Type K thermocouples (TC, 1.5 mm encapsulated) measured temperatures along the centreline ($Y=125\text{ cm}$), 1 cm above the fuel bed at $X=30, 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350$ and 372 cm from the left edge ($X=0\text{ cm}$). Two plate thermocouples (PTC, 0.4 mm Inconel) were placed at $X=150\text{ cm}$ and 250 cm along the back edge ($Y=250\text{ cm}$), and one at $X=402\text{ cm}$ along the centreline ($Y=125\text{ cm}$), with 10 cm from plate centre to set-up surface. One TC was positioned mid-air 1 cm above each PTC. The uncertainty of the temperature measurement was $\pm 2\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Black and white steel sticks were used to visually determine the flame length (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Experimental setup with measurements (a). Red dots are TCs (b), red triangles are plate TCs (c), and black/white sticks are for visual observations of flame length.

2.1. Fuels

Figure 2: Fuels used in the experiments: (a) fine spruce wood chips, (b) pine wood fibre and (c) juniper.

Selected fuels were fine spruce wood chips (9.5wt% moisture content, 97.1 kg/m^3 bulk density), less fine spruce wood chips ($\sim 9.3\text{wt}\%$, 92.0 kg/m^3), loose-fill pine wood fibre (12.7wt%, 7.30 kg/m^3),

and Juniper (*J communis*, 46.0wt%), and combinations of these (Figure 2). Wood chips and loose-fill wood fibre were chosen as they are cellulose-based with dimensions common for forest litter but with more well-defined properties, enabling studies of e.g. fuel bed density effects. The juniper was included since it is known to give intense torching fires. A total of 11 experiments are presented here with detailed information provided in Table 1 in the following section.

3. Results and discussion

Characteristic experimental results (wood fibre, experiment 2) are shown in Figure 3. The flame front progression can be seen from the temperature rise on the side (a) and the centre of the fuel bed (c). The mass loss and mass loss rate (MLR, using 60 seconds averaging) (b) coincides with the main burning period. Using a TC threshold of 50 °C to indicate flame arrival, the rate of flame spread (ROS) was calculated for each 50 cm section and averaged for the whole experiment and was on par with visual observations. For the densely packed fuel beds (wood chips, or wood chips on top of wood fibre), ROS could not be obtained by temperature measurements, due to the non-1D fire spread.

Figure 3: Measurements from Experiment 2. a) showing the plate thermocouple temperature (PTC) and the gas temperature (TC), b) mass loss over time and mass loss rate and c) the gas temperatures.

The fireline intensity (FI , kW/m) is defined as $FI = Hwr$ [18], where H is the low heat of combustion (kJ/kg), w is the fuel consumed (kg/m^2) and r is the rate of spread (m/s). The heat of combustion used was 16 MJ/kg, as used by Bøe et al. [19] for Norwegian spruce.

Table 1: Summary of the experimental parameters and results: material, fuel load, percentage of the mass consumed, rate of flame spread (ROS), standard deviation (SD) of ROS, fireline intensity (FI), and the maximum flame length.

Experiment/fuel	#1 Chips dense	#2 Fibre	#3 Fibre	#4 Fibre on Chips	#5 Chips on Fibre	#6 Fibre + Juniper
Fuel load (MJ/m^2)	80	12	12	46	46	16
Mass loss (%)	6	100	100	26	100	96
ROS (m/min)	<u>0.12-0.24</u>	1.1	1.0	1.0	<u>0.36-0.67</u>	1.2
SD of ROS		0.19	0.08	0.11		0.12
FI (kW/m)	<u>7-13</u>	215	215	183	<u>25-119</u>	307
Max. flame length (m)	0.05	0.80	0.80	0.50	0.2	1.0 (2.5*)
Experiment/fuel	#7 Chips less dense	#8 Fibre + Juniper	#9 Fibre, tilt	#10 Fibre, tilt	#11 Chips less dense, tilt	
Fuel load (MJ/m^2)	67	16	12	12	67	
Mass loss (%)	9	95	100	100	10	
ROS (m/min)	<u>0.09-0.23</u>	1.4	4.7	5.0	<u>0.21-0.43</u>	
SD of ROS		0.20	1.47	2.29		
FI (kW/m)	<u>3-11</u>	379	594	700	<u>11-43</u>	
Max. flame length (m)	0.05-0.07	0.80 (3.0*)	1.2-1.5	1.2-2	0.05-0.1	

*Flame length of juniper. X: Range and calculation is based on visual observations on the irregular fire front.

Experiments #2 and #3 were repetitions and produced highly similar results. Wood chips (#1, 97 kg/m³ and #7, 82 kg/m³) burnt only marginally, even when subject to a 20° tilt (#11). Repeatability was indicatively good (#2 and #3). Loose wood fibres placed on top of denser wood chips (#4) burnt similar to wood fibres alone and resulted in a faster and more intense flame compared to the reversed layering (#5) which was similar to wood chips alone. Chips on top of fibres slowly and irregularly consumed all fuel. Junipers clusters (total mass of 2.2 and 2.5 kg, height ~50-70 cm) were added in #6 and #8, giving a drastic local increase in the fire intensity (Figure 4). The same conditions as #2 and #3, but with a 20° inclination, drastically increased flames, ROS and FI in #9 and #10 (Table 1). The small standard deviation for horizontal experiments indicates a steady fire spread while the larger standard deviation in experiments with inclination suggests that the fire spread is less steady. Another method to check whether the fire reaches steady state is conducting linear regression on the data of ‘flame front position *v.* time’ for positions X=50 cm to X=350 cm, which achieves fairly high correlation coefficients ($R^2 > 0.997$) for wood fibre tests, except in Experiment 9 ($R^2 = 0.990$) and experiment 10 ($R^2 = 0.986$). Compared with correlations of ROS, FI and flame length developed for Calluna-dominated fuels by Davies et al. [20,21], the wood fibre in the experiments shows slightly larger ROS (1 m/min vs. 0.79 m/min) and slightly smaller flame length (0.8 m vs. 1.04 m), while a much larger fireline intensity (215 kW/m vs. 99.77 kW/m). For fuel beds with inclination, Silvani et al. [22] suggest that as slope increases, the radiation dominated thermal environment ahead of the flame front is progressively turned into a mixed convective-radiative one, in which convection finally dominated for steep slope configurations. In Silvani et al. (2012), the fuel depth of pine excelsior is 6.2-6.3 cm, the ROS changes from 13.1 mm/s (0.79 m/min) with no slope to 33.7 mm/s (2.0 m/min) with 20° slope. For wood fibre experiments in this study, ROS is changed from about 1 m/min with zero slope to about 5 m/min with 20° slope, which is larger than that in Silvani et al. [22].

Figure 4 shows three different stages of the fires in experiments 1, 3, 6 and 9. Notice that the 20° inclination (experiment 9 and 10) with fibre gave 4-5 times higher ROS than that of the horizontal fuel bed. A similar behaviour was also found for chips. This is similar to findings done in other laboratory experiments on inclined fuel beds [23,24], although with varying inclination and spread rate increase. ROS and FI are based on 1D fire spread, but for the most densely compacted fuel beds the marginal spread was quite irregular, burning only the top layer and leaving uncharred patches— similar to that observed in field studies of well-compacted fuel beds under certain spruce stands [25]. The lighter and more aerated fuel of wood fibres consumed all fuels with a steady flame front. The ROS of 1 m/min with wood fibre was close to that of laboratory studies of heather (*C vulgaris*) shrubs with no wind [26] or controlled prescribed fire [27] on heather moorlands. Fireline intensities for the tilted experiments presented here are comparable to that of Hancock et al. [25] (mean 420 and 520 kW/m).

Figure 4: Pictures taken prior to ignition, at halfway burning and after flameout of experiment 1, 3, 6 and 9 with wood chips, wood fibre, fibre and juniper, and testbed inclination, respectively.

One aim of the study is to investigate if natural fires can be reliably mimicked in the lab. The results are here compared with a number of ongoing field experimental campaigns in boreal and hemiboreal Sweden [28,29], where characteristic fire behaviour in various fuel types is investigated. The campaigns involve forest stands dominated by Scots pine, Norway spruce, some deciduous species, as well as heather and grasslands. We define normal dry conditions involving fine fuel mc of 10 – 12 % and 2 – 4 m/s wind. Likewise, severe scenarios involve fine fuel mc of 7 – 8 % and wind speed of 5 – 6 m/s. Note that heather fuel moisture will always be higher (around 60 %). Characteristic values from field experiments are presented in Table 2. Only continuous surface spread on flat terrain is considered, while spotting, torching or crowning are not considered. Results show that the ROS and flame length of tilted wood fibre obtained in the lab are comparable to the parameters measured in normal dry conditions but need additional aerated fuel for heather of severe forest conditions.

Table 2: Characteristic values from field experiments done in boreal and hemiboreal Sweden [28,29].

Fuel type	Normal dry conditions		Severe conditions	
	ROS (m/min)	Flame length (m)	ROS (m/min)	Flame length (m)
Pine	1.5 – 3.0	0.7 – 1.4	6 - 12	1 – 2
Spruce	0.8 – 2.0	0.4 – 0.8	2 – 4	0.8 – 1.4
Heather	2.0 – 4.0	1.0 – 2.0	8 – 14	2 – 3
Grasslands	3.0 – 10.0	0.7 – 1.5	10 – 20	1 – 2

4. Conclusions

A series of large lab-scale experiments were conducted to study how to mimic Scandinavian heathland and boreal forest wildfires using laboratory standardized fuels. Densely packed fuel bed (fine wood chips of 82-97 kg/m³ bulk density) exhibited marginal irregular burning with only little fuel consumption. Flame spread for 5 cm high (0.7 kg/m²) wood fibre was close to 1D with a spread rate of about 1 m/min and a fireline intensity just above ~200 kW/m and flame length reaching 0.8 m. With juniper placed in the fuel bed together with the wood fibre, the flame length was increased to almost 3 m and an increase in spread rate and fireline intensity was also found. Inclination of 20° increased the wood fibre fire spread rate by a factor 4-5 compared to the horizontal case while flame length increased by ~50% and fireline intensity more than doubled. Compared with wildfire characteristics from ongoing field studies in boreal and hemiboreal Sweden, the lab fire experiments could be tailored to mimic standardised design scenarios of relevant natural Scandinavian wildfire conditions.

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